

A Low-Cost Measurement Setup to Test Low-Power Voltage Transformers in the 9 kHz – 150 kHz Frequency Range

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Abstract— The increasing integration of renewable resources in the energy mix of countries leads to a certain degradation of the quality of electricity due to the use of electronic power converters. The latter, composed of switching components, can introduce high frequency harmonics up to 150 kHz into the network. However, the international standards and state-of-art literature of instruments transformers (ITs) do not adequately cover or even address methods, techniques, parameters, and metrological requirements to be followed during power quality (PQ) measurements in case of frequencies greater than tens of kilohertz. In this framework, this paper proposes a new method and a measurement setup, performed with economical instrumentation, for characterizing two medium voltage (MV) low-power voltage transformers (LPVTs) in the extended frequency range 9 – 150 kHz. In detail, this work applies the “sinc-approach” which is a new characterization procedure, previously designed by the authors, that has several advantages enumerated later. After the description of the scenario behind this work, the measurement setup, tests, and results are described in depth in order to propose a preliminary simple and low-cost harmonic characterization procedure of LPVTs in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

Keywords—Low-power Voltage Transformers, Power Quality, Harmonic Analysis, 9 – 150 kHz, Medium Voltage, Frequency Characterization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The previous model of electric power network characterized by (i) centralization of power generation, (ii) unidirectional energy flows and (iii) a strong prevalence of non-renewable forms of energy is being replaced by the future model called smart grid. Smart grids are based on distributed generation with the presence of bidirectional power flows and an important percentage of renewable energy sources. Despite the numerous benefits of this new type of infrastructure, the problem of power quality (PQ) degradation is becoming non-negligible, because, to feed energy into the grid, green energies (wind and photovoltaic mainly) need power electronic converters which are among the causes of PQ reduction [1]. Therefore, the international context of growing energy demand, combined with the need to reduce environmental impact, is pushing towards to an ever-greater integration of renewable energy sources at all voltage levels and particularly in MV energy distribution systems. Consequently, the disturbances caused by power converters are putting the stability of electrical systems under pressure, because, due to the high frequency switching of electronic components, this type of converter can inject harmonics up to 150 kHz into the network [2]. In general, the presence of harmonics is the cause of (i) overheating of components, (ii)

power losses, (iii) failure of electronic components, (iv) intervention of protections and many other unwanted events that lead to economic losses and reduced safety [3]. Therefore, reliable PQ measurements are important to monitor the true state of the network and prevent the occurrence of faults. Otherwise, if the results to the measurements are inaccurate, the above-mentioned undesired events may occur. In conclusion, since ITs are commonly used for current and voltage measurements in MV networks, their behavior vs. this new set of frequencies is becoming a hot research topic.

Within the academic community, the study of the characterization of MV ITs with respect to frequency has been prolific. For example, in 50 Hz systems, the traditional PQ band up to 2.5 kHz is addressed in many works and using different types of devices: (i) inductive current transformer [4, 5], (ii) conventional voltage transformer [6, 7], and finally low-power instrument transformers (LPITs) [8, 9]. However, the accuracy of MV ITs vs. frequency over the extended frequency range 2 – 150 kHz is less investigated. On the other hand, an increasing number of high-frequency harmonics is injected by power electronic converters into the networks. Therefore, in order to enhance the knowledge about ITs behavior, in the recent years scientific research on the characterization of the ITs frequency response is particularly active. For example, the EURAMET project number 19NRM05 IT4PQ [10] aimed to define new accuracy limits, parameters, and tests for PQ measurements of currents and voltages with a spectral content up to 9 kHz when using MV ITs. One of the objectives of IT4PQ was the creation of scientific literature so that the IEC Technical Committee 38 may update the actual standards to the new operating conditions of ITs. After the conclusion of IT4PQ, a recent EURAMET project number 22NRM06 ADMIT [11] has as its main intent to expand the frequency spectrum under analysis by bringing the upper limit of voltages and currents to be measured from 9 kHz to 150 kHz (in what follows, a section is dedicated to the description of the current research in that frequency range).

In such framework, this paper presents a fast and low-cost harmonic characterization procedure for MV LPVTs in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. It is important to underline that the focus of this work is not on the fundamental frequency, because this frequency component is well-covered in depth in the standards. Furthermore, standard procedures for testing ITs in the selected frequency range are not available yet. Hence, the paper does not include any comparison with existing solutions (performed in previously published papers).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the context in which the work carried out fits. Then, Section III contains the description of the “sinc-approach” and

measurement setup. Finally, Section IV and V reports experimental results and conclusion, respectively.

II. SCENARIO

A. Low-power instrument transformers

Low-power instrument transformers, also called “non-conventional instrument transformers” in the past, were designed and developed in order to overcome the limitations of the traditional iron-core ITs. In fact, the advent of smart grids has introduced new requirements during the monitoring and management of the power network. In particular, in MV applications, the adoption of LPITs is growing thanks to their numerous advantages over conventional ITs, such as: (i) output voltage level compatible with intelligent electronic devices (i.e. millivolt to some Volt), (ii) wide frequency response (i.e. extended linearity thanks to the lack of the ferromagnetic core), (iii) smaller in size and therefore requires less space, and finally (iv) lighter in weight and therefore are easier to install [12]. However, the main drawbacks can be summarized in: (i) a lower accuracy compared to ITs under nominal network working conditions and (ii) a lower stability of this type of device over time due to susceptibility to various external agents such as: temperature, vibrations and magnetic fields [13].

B. The 9 kHz – 150 kHz frequency range

As this work is supported by ADMIT, the frequency range of interest is 9 – 150 kHz. To the author's knowledge, there are no shared international standards that regulate this portion of frequencies of interest at MV level with regards to equipment, tests, accuracy specifications and measurements techniques. For example, ITs standards focus almost exclusively on the fundamental frequency component. The IEC 61869 family of standards, which deals with every aspect of ITs, states accuracy specifications only in the case of quantities having a frequency spectrum lower than the 50th harmonics (of the fundamental) for a.c. applications and 20 kHz for d.c. applications, according to the recently published IEC 61869-1:2023 [14], which merged two general standards into a single one, i.e. the IEC 61869-1:2007 [15] and IEC 61869-6:2016 [16]. In addition, there is also the IEC 61869-103:2012 [17] which is a technical report that suggests some tests, parameters, guidelines, and especially new specific accuracy classes for PQ measurements, but some of them are not yet defined in the standard itself. In addition, even the family of Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) standards 61000 does not suggest accuracy requirements for transducers installed in MV systems.

On the other hand, with reference to the limits of harmonic emissions in MV power systems, the IEEE 519 [18] and IEC 50160 [19] specify limits for the characteristics of the grid voltage at the point of common coupling of user's supply terminal. However, the highest standardized harmonic order is the 50th of the fundamental.

In the last few years, the state of the art is starting to focus on the behavior of MV transducers in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. For example, [20] provides an extensive review of all transducer and in particular their accuracy in measuring harmonic components. However, the main focus is the range 2 – 9 kHz. While, up to 150 kHz, [21] proposes an exploratory analysis of the transfer function of MV ITs and LPITs, while [22] explores the frequency response of power transformers.

In conclusion, researchers are trying to fill the knowledge gap present in international standards and in the state of art by

proposing consolidated and shared guidelines and not just suggestions, which can improve how system operators manages their assets.

C. Motivation

Since LPITs are key elements for performing electrical measurements of the power network, the knowledge on their frequency characterization is particularly active and continuously expanding over time. Therefore, this paper aims to broaden the field applications of a new procedure developed by the authors for characterizing LPVTs frequency response. The novel working condition is the extended frequency range 9 – 150 kHz. The proposed method, called “sinc-approach”, is implemented inside a low-cost measurement setup. The proposed procedure offers: (i) reduced testing time (and consequently saving money); (ii) simpler measurement process; (iii) the use of economical low-voltage instrumentation for the generation of testing signal.

III. SINC-APPROACH

A. Method Overview

The theory behind the “sinc-approach” is developed in [23, 24], and a brief description is provided here.

The first step is the design of the sinc testing signal, during which the following three main parameters must be considered: (i) the total number of samples of the waveform depending on the memory of the arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), (ii) the frequency resolution of the waveform and finally (iii) the cut-off frequency of the spectrum under analysis. In fact, in the frequency domain, if the spectrum of the discrete sinc function is centered on zero, it has a rectangular shape having at its ends the desired value of the cut-off frequency. Then, the second step is to apply the Blackman window to the designed sinc function to reduce the spectral leakage due to truncation during the AWG generation. In this application, the designed windowed sinc signal (WSS) is composed by 8192 samples with a period of 0.5 ms and a frequency content up to 150 kHz. Finally, the third step is to apply the WSS to the device under test to acquire its frequency response that can be called sinc response (SR). In conclusion, with a single measurement, it is possible to achieve a selected portion of the frequency response with the desired resolution and consequently it is possible to evaluate the accuracy of the LPVTs under test. On the other hand, traditional method, such as the well-known frequency sweep, can be more time-consuming as the number of tests is proportional to the number of tested frequencies. Therefore, if the frequency range of interest is very large and the analysis of the spectrum is performed with small frequency steps, even automated systems can have non-negligible work times.

Overall, the added value of this paper is the integration between the “sinc-approach” and a low-cost measurement setup. This is done in a field of application not covered by standards. In detail, the proposed procedure allows for characterizing LPVTs in the frequency range 9 - 150 kHz with a single measurement test.

B. Measurement setup

The measurement setup adopted in this work is represented by the block diagram in Fig. 1. It consists of: (i) two AWGs Rigol DG1022Z with a frequency resolution of 1 μ Hz, (ii) a precision operational amplifier ADHV4702-1 included in its evaluation board, which has a wide range of operating voltages up to ± 105 V (Table I summarizes the main features of the OP-AMP), (iii) two LPVTs (Table II reports

the main characteristics of the devices under test) and finally (iv) an oscilloscope Tektronix MSO58 (Table III summarizes the main features of the oscilloscope).

In a nutshell, AWG_1 provides an external clock reference signal $v_{clock}(t)$ to AWG_2 and oscilloscope. This voltage is a 10 MHz square wave used to synchronize the generation and the acquisition of the measurement chain. Then, AWG_2 generates the designed WSS $v_{sinc}(t)$, which is then amplified by the OP-AMP and applied to the LPVTs under test. Finally, the oscilloscope acquires the primary voltage $v_p(t)$ applied to the device under test and its secondary output voltage $v_s(t)$.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the measurement setup

TABLE I. MAIN FEATURES OF THE OP-AMP

Dual supply	± 12 V to ± 110 V	CMRR	160 dB
Slew rate	24 V/ μ s	Input bias current	2 pA
Bandwidth	10 MHz	Input offset voltage	1 mV

TABLE II. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LPVTs

	LPVT 1	LPVT 2
Technology	Passive capacitive	Active closed loop fluxgate
Transformation Ratio [-]	5981	100
Primary voltage [kV]	30	1
Accuracy class [-]	0.2	0.2

TABLE III. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OSCILLOSCOPE

Bandwidth	350 MHz	ADC resolution	16 bits
Input impedance	1 M Ω with 13 pF	Maximum sampling frequency	6.25 GSa/s
Maximum input voltage	300 V _{RMS}	Maximum Volts/div setting	10 V/div

C. Description of the test

The idea behind the proposed method is to collect the SR of the LPVTs under test. According to the Annex C of the IEC 61000-4-30 [25], the AWG provides an appropriate WSS, designed by the operator, which has a period of 0.5 ms and a frequency content up to 150 kHz. Then, this voltage waveform is amplified by the OP-AMP and applied to the input of the LPVTs under test. Afterwards, the input and output (i.e. the SR) of the LPVTs are acquired by the oscilloscope and the samples are stored in the memory of a PC. In particular, 100 repeated measurements are performed, and, for each measurement, 10 cycles are recorded. Finally, the fast Fourier transform (FFT) is calculated over one period to obtain the frequency spectrum with a resolution of 2 kHz. Therefore, the frequency range under analysis is adjusted to 8 – 150 kHz.

Regarding the test signal generation side, the OP-AMP is slow rate limited which means the amplitude of the frequency components tends to decrease as the harmonic order increases, as it can be seen in Fig. 2. Therefore, the frequency characterization of the OP-AMP is not trivial, since the sinc function a multi-tone signal and the effect of the slew rate on the WSS depends on: (i) the harmonics amplitude, (ii) the harmonics order and (iii) the number of the harmonics that make up the tested waveform. In conclusion, for a matter of simplicity, it is more convenient to acquire the OP-AMP output directly. To this purpose, considering that the peak of the amplified sinc function is around 75 V and the sampling rate needs to be sufficiently high, an oscilloscope is used as acquisition device.

Fig. 2. Amplitude spectrum of OP-AMP output

Regarding the oscilloscope setup, the vertical settings of each channel are adjusted separately during the tests in order to optimize the resolution of the ADC. The sampling frequency is set to 5 MSa/s corresponding to a bandwidth equal to 2 MHz.

IV. RESULTS

To assess the experimental results, for each harmonic components of interest, the ratio error and composite error are calculated according to the following equations:

$$\varepsilon_h(\%) = \frac{K_r U_{s,h} - U_{p,h}}{U_{p,h}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_c(\%) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum (K_r u_s[n] - u_p[n])^2}}{U_{p,h}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

The two formulas includes the following parameters: (i) the rated transformation ratio K_r of the LPVTs under test, (ii)

the rms harmonic components of order h of the primary and secondary, $U_{p,h}$ and $U_{s,h}$, respectively, (iii) the total number of considered samples N and finally (iv) the sequence of samples of the primary and secondary, $u_p[n]$ and $u_s[n]$, respectively. In this work, the primary signal is the output of the OP-AMP, while the secondary signal comes from the LPVTs under test. It is important to underline that the composite error is reported in the discrete form in the time-domain, while its most commonly cited definition, for example in [14], involves an integral instead of the summation as the composite error is an index created for use with continuous time-domain signals. This accuracy parameter combines the amplitude and phase variation of the two waveforms under test, so this is a more rigorous index than the traditional ratio error which involves only the amplitudes. This is why, even if mainly defined and used for current transformer, the composite error is introduced in the evaluation of the LPVTs accuracy in this extended frequency range.

All the obtained results are presented in Fig. 3 and 4 and in Table IV. In particular, Fig. 3 and 4 shows how the ratio error of the two LPVTs under test varies with respect to frequency. While Table IV reports the obtained values of the composite error. All values are calculated as the average of the 100 measurements performed during each acquisition.

Fig. 3. Ratio error vs. frequency of LPVT 1

Fig. 4. Ratio error vs. frequency of LPVT 2

In Fig. 3 and 4, as suggested in the Annex C of the IEC 61000-4-30 [25], the x-axis frequency step is equal to 2 kHz. For both LPVTs, it can be observed that the error never exceeds 2 %. Therefore, the precision achieved is notable, in fact, the IEC 61869-1 [14] recommends that the maximum ratio error of an LPVT of accuracy class 0.2 must not exceed 16 % for frequencies above the 13^o harmonics. However, the trend over frequency is different. In particular, the behavior of LPVT 1 is mostly random at lower frequencies and tends to stabilize at higher frequencies. While the ratio error of LPVT 2, expressed in percentage, decreases as the frequency increases.

TABLE IV. COMPOSITE ERROR OF LPVTs UNDER TEST

	LPVT 1	LPVT 2
$\varepsilon_c(\%)$	7	6

The idea behind Table IV is to introduce the composite error as an index that can improve the knowledge of the metrological performance of the devices under test, since the standards are more oriented toward using only the ratio error and phase displacement. Due to the novel use of this index, the values in Table IV cannot be compared with standards. However, the obtained percentages are coherent with the distortions included in the signal and the physical meaning of the index.

Fig. 5. Amplitude spectrum of OP-AMP and LPVT 1 outputs

Finally, Fig. 5 exhibits a portion of the signal acquired from the OP-AMP and LPVT 1 outputs; the latter multiplied by the respective transformation ratio, so the moderate mismatch between LPVT input-output can be appreciated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The characterization of the frequency response of MV voltage sensors is a research topic that over the years is shifting the focus of the analysis towards increasingly higher frequencies in order to keep up with the evolution of the power networks in which this type of devices is installed. Currently, the extended frequency range 9 – 150 kHz is under study. Therefore, in the absence of indications from the standards, a preliminary fast and simple characterization procedure is proposed. In particular, a new method, called “sinc-approach”, is used for evaluating the behavior over frequency of two commercial LPVTs in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. This technique was developed with the aim of simplifying and reducing testing times and consequently the costs that manufacturers and system operators incur during the sensor development and testing. In addition, the measurements are performed using low-cost and low-voltage instrumentation, so the procedure can be easily exploited even outside large research centers. Moving forward, starting from the results obtained in this paper, a reference test will be carried out with equipment in metrological validation to confirm the effectiveness of the proposed procedure by comparison. Furthermore, time intervals longer than 0.5 ms will be analyzed in order to have a higher frequency resolution and therefore a more detailed analysis of the frequency behavior of the test sensors.

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